

TYPE OF MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION.

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Annotation: Correct organization of the management system in the preschool education system is one of the main tasks of today. There are various important types of management in the preschool education system, and the article provides information about them.

Keywords: continuous, improvement, knowledge, , plan, subject, principle, incentive, method, laws, functions, planning, management, design.

Annotatsiya: Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv tizimini to'g'ri tashkil etish bugungi kunning asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida boshqarishni turli xil ahamiyatli turlari mavjud bo'lib, maqolada shular haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: uzluksiz, takomillashtirish, bilish, , reja, predmet, tamoyil, rag'bat, metod, qonuniyatlar, funsiyalar, rejalashtirish, boshqarish, loyihalashtirish.

Аннотация: Правильная организация системы управления в системе дошкольного образования является одной из главных задач современности. В системе дошкольного образования существуют различные важные виды управления, и в статье представлена информация о них.

Ключевые слова: непрерывный, совершенствование, знание, план, предмет, принцип, стимул, метод, законы, функции, планирование, управление, проектирование.

The field of preschool education is considered the primary branch of the system of continuing education, which is of paramount importance in all aspects in the

upbringing and preparation of the personality of a healthy and harmonious child for school. During the years of independence, the education system and upbringing of a harmonious generation in the Republic rose to the level of the main priorities of state policy. However, the analysis carried out shows that the results and results of work carried out in the field of preschool education are insufficient. In particular, over the past 20 years, the number of state-owned preschools has decreased by more than 45 percent, and today the coverage of children in the Republic with preschool education is 30 percent. Also, the material and technical base of preschool educational organizations does not meet modern demand.

No variational programs have been introduced in the preschool system, alternative, flexible models for preparing children for school have not developed sufficiently, and special state educational programs aimed at social, personal, emotional, speech, Mathematical, Physical and creative development, acquaintance with the environment have not been implemented, like developed countries. Most of the pedagogical personnel operating in state preschool educational organizations have a secondary special education, which does not allow to prepare children at the level of demand for school education. In addition, since the monitoring of the quality of preschool education is not provided for structurally and organizationally, the assessment of the quality and effectiveness of the educational process in preschool educational organizations does not meet the requirements of the Times. The analysis of the advanced experience of foreign countries is characterized by the orientation to create conditions for the development of preschool children in modern preschool educational organizations, aimed at demonstrating the possibilities of positive socialization of the child, his comprehensive spiritual and moral and conscious development of the individual, the development of initiative and creative abilities based on the relevant types of activities

The laws of Educational Management reflect the objectively existing, recurring interactions of various elements and phenomena in the management process. They are divided into general and private. Common laws are inherent in all systems of management, while special ones are associated with the validity of certain educational organizations and organizations. The following can be included in the list of General Laws of management: priority efficiency and conscious planned management;

strengthening the processes of interaction of managed and managed systems, the subject and object of management, division and cooperation of labor in management. Let's look at these laws.

The priority effectiveness of conscious management of education is legitimate, since the system of planned management of the processes taking place in it is more effective than control systems that in practice involuntarily regulate these processes. The fact that software-targeted approach, systematic approach and analysis are widely used at all levels of Management in current education is evidence of this.

Systems that are managed and managed indicate that the relationship of the subject and object of management is legal in accordance with the requirements of the object of management of the sphere of management. Chunonchi, a noticeable shift in the development of the economy from the mid-90s required a certain change in the entire management apparatus in our country, which was reflected in the complex of reforms in education and training of Personnel, which began in 1997. As a result, the system of education and its management has acquired the principle of sustainable development in accordance with the requirements of socio-economic, political changes, development of Science and technology.

The strengthening of the division of Labor and cooperative processes in management can also be included in the General Laws of Educational Management. The law, firstly, reflects the further horizontal and vertical distribution of labor in management, this is due to the fact that management has developed, the scope of managed systems has expanded, new functions and types of activities have appeared. Secondly, the division of Labor assumes its coordination, that is, the Coordination of the work of the subjects of Management, which is expressed in the cooperation of managerial labor. If general laws are specific to governance in general, private laws are specific to certain aspects and systems of governance.

The following can be included in the order of private laws: such as changes in management functions, the approval of the number of stages of management, the concentration of management functions and the law of prevalence of control.

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